

An Investigation of Food Photography and Consumption Behaviour in 18-29-Year Olds

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ABSTRACT

Purpose – Beyond nourishing the body, food has been recognized as a symbol of social cohesion, identity, and culture. As social media grows more pervasive, the behaviour toward food photography has become more refined in today's digital age. The purpose of this study is to examine the consumption behaviours, motivations, and cultural dimensions of 18-29 years old through the food visuals on Instagram.

Methodology – The study works within an interpretive paradigm to better understand the phenomenon of food photography. Based on eight participants, an inductive qualitative approach using the combination of semi-structured interview and photo-elicitation method is adopted.

Findings – Firstly, there is a positive link between food photography on Instagram and food consumption behaviour. Secondly, both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation influence the enthusiasm of posting food photography. Thirdly, it is not proven that a person with high level of indulgence and individualism culture tend to involve more in food photography compared to an individual of restraint and collectivism culture.

Practical Implications – Treated as the fourth objective, there are three recommendations provided; to build 'customer engagement', focusing on 'content marketing' and customers as a part of the 'digital promotion'. With these recommendations, food industry will engage more efficiently with the rise of social media and consumption behaviour in the future.

Originality/value – This study explores beyond the theme of food photography, specifically in terms of cultural dimensions, which has not been studied before.

Keywords – food photography, Instagram, social media, consumption behaviour, motivation, culture

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1. DEFINITION OF THE TOPIC

Food is more than just a fuel for bodies but also a vital part of culture, pleasure, belonging and identity (Ibrahim, 2015). According to LeBesco and Naccarato (2017), food has become more intertwined with the popular culture as chefs have transformed into celebrities-chefs and cooking has extended its reach across the media landscape. Both visual and sensory modes are saturated due to the excessive publicity of food, especially through social media, television, magazines, newspapers, specialist food blogs and many more (Ibrahim, 2015). Moreover, these platforms often portray food as perfect, using visual effects and aesthetic features (Zukin and Maguire, 2004). In relation to food consumption behaviour, brain is the body's most blood-thirsty organ that is actively evolved to find food (Spence, 2017). Interestingly, Thring (2012) found that images of food activated brain regions that control appetite and reward, where Schüssler et al (2012) reported that visual exposure increases self-rated appetite and eating behaviour in humans.

Consumers are no longer merely passive recipients in the marketing exchange process (Hanna, Rohm and Crittenden, 2011). According to Hansen, Shneiderman and Smith (2011), social media platforms have engendered radically new ways of interacting that successfully build the strongest communities with the most dynamic conversations. Additionally, Pennel (2018) highlights the importance of mobile device ownership that positively correlates with the rise of social media. Particularly, Figure 1.1 shows that among young adults (ages 18-29), social media use has reached approximately 90% and is still growing (Perrin, 2015). Young adults and teens, a population labelled as 'Generation Yum' by Turow (2015), find themselves at the forefront of this food, social, and mobile media movement. As a result, the 'food photography'

phenomenon has gone from being a niche and eccentric practice to being extremely popular due to aspiring social media personalities specifically from this generation (Tropnikova, 2017).

Figure 1.1: Young adults (18-29) are the most likely to use social media

(Source: Perrin, 2015)

Nowadays, the ability to share images on the Internet is undeniably faster and more convenient due to the rapid growth of social media (Lyon, 2017). Food photography, in particular, has become part of self-representation, daily posts, and competitive likes on social media (Lovell, 2017). There are several social media platforms adopted as visual representation such as Facebook, that enables users to post and engage a variety of content through photos and status updates (Stec, 2018). Moreover, Twitter is a micro-blogging platform containing a limited number of characters (Nations, 2017) and Snapchat accumulated a core concept of temporary pictures, videos and messages (Betters, 2018). Finally, Instagram emphasizes photo and video-sharing through mobile phones (Moreau, 2018). Since Instagram is the most hyper-visual creature platform of visual representation (Kugel, 2017), this particular study will be focusing on Instagram as the key social media platform.

Due to the motives behind hashtags (#) and geotag (location identification), *Figure 1.2* depicts Instagram as the most popular platform especially within the culinary tourism (Saufi et al., 2017). Consistently, according to Webstagram (web-based that ranks Instagram images by popularity), *#food* always positions as in the top 25 hashtags worldwide (Ibrahim, 2015). Mejova, Abbar and Haddadi (2016) also found that *#foodporn* has occupied 46% of approximately 10 million Instagram posts. Food porn is defined as “the act of styling and capturing food on mobile gadgets, eliciting an invitation to gaze, consume, and tag images of food through digital platforms” (Ibrahim, 2015, p.2). Thus, it is perhaps inevitable that visual representation of food has been one of the fastest growing topics on Instagram due to great eagerness to share food online (Tandoh, 2016).

Figure 1.2. Comparison of Food Hashtags on Different Social Media Platforms

	Instagram	Tumblr	Flickr	Youtube	Twitter
#foodgasm #foodporn #tourism	39,400	2,920	1,840	4,290	4,760
Seconds	0.47	0.40	0.43	0.21	0.44
#foodgasm #foodporn #culinarytourism	64	No results	9	7	5
Seconds	0.52	-	0.79	0.41	0.40
Related hashtags	#foodie #foodphotography #foodculture #foodtravel #foodblogger #taste #gastronomy	#realfoodtravel #eating #tasty #yummy #delicious	#foodadventure #vacation #holiday #travelgram #instatraveling #foodpic #cuisine	#traveler #instatravel #culinary #tourism	#foody #travel #travelling #foodoftheday

(Source: Saufi et al., 2017)

1.2. AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The phenomenal growth of digital technology has impacted in almost every aspect of daily lives over the past two decades (Duffett, 2017). In today's digital age, social media uses the 'wisdom of crowds' to connect information in a collaborative manner (Neti, 2011). For instance, collaborative tagging and social search are among the most successful applications (Zeng et al., 2010). Furthermore, food is often viewed as a socialising focus and means for simultaneous enriching experiences, expressing personal identities and adding quality of life (Yeoman and McMahon-Beatte, 2016). Moreover, Ibrahim (2015) found that images are seen as a vital part of the connectivity to express everyday flows of life and human communion.

The concept 'food photography' was coined by Rosalind Coward, an American Feminist Critic in 1984 (Dabrowska, 2016). This concept has a very specific genre as it demands passion and a deep understanding of the food products that connects with the appetite (Dabrowska, 2016). However, Baker (2013) certified that the disruption and incessant camera flashes of photographing food have led many leading restaurants to ban food photography. Some restaurants were also discontented with customers letting food get cold since photos cannot represent the quality of the flavours (Petter, 2017). Despite the criticisms, Spence et al (2016) established that an increase in natural desire to see food images, referred as 'visual hunger', is presumably the reason why it remains rewarding in the digital age.

The main aim of this research is to investigate on how the rise of social media, particularly Instagram, influence the age group of 18-29 on food consumption. The four main objectives are listed as follows:

1. To investigate the link between food photography on Instagram and food consumption behaviour.
2. To explore which type of motivation influences 18-29-year olds foodie's enthusiasm of posting food photography on Instagram.

3. To prove whether a person with high level of indulgence and individualism culture tend to involve more in food photography compared to an individual of restraint and collectivism cultures.
4. To provide recommendations for food industry on how to engage more efficiently with the rise of social media and consumption behaviour in the future.

The next chapter provides a further evaluation of the food photography literature and critically analyses the information gathered by identifying gaps from previous studies. In terms of the methodology, primary data is utilised, which is the original data collected for the specific research goal, using procedures that fit the research objectives best (Hox and Boije, 2005). The researcher believes that the qualitative combination of semi-structured interview and photo-elicitation method is appropriate given the nature of this research paper. Then, the fourth chapter will focus on analysing the research findings and accomplish the first three objectives set by the researcher. Finally, the last chapter will conclude why this study was conducted in the first place, including practical recommendations for the food industry, which is presented as the fourth objective of this paper.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. INTRODUCTION

This chapter summaries the literature that relates to social media marketing focusing on Instagram, the phenomenon of food photography and trend of food consumption behaviour in order to provide several theoretical foundations for the rest of the study. Firstly, photography theory and consumption behaviour are introduced to explain the food consumption behaviour by the age group 18-29. Secondly, the motivation behind the ‘foodie’ culture on social media is deeply assessed to understand the theories behind the decision of performing food photography of the target group. Finally, the assessment of food photography in relation to cultural dimensions is illustrated to achieve a prominent understanding of the link between food photography and consumption behaviour across the world, where Hofstede’s cultural dimension theory is adopted as a paradigm across cross-cultural domain.

2.2. PHOTOGRAPHY THEORY AND FOOD CONSUMPTION BEHAVIOUR

Photography is a form of non-verbal communication, it conveys a thought from the photographer to the viewer (Barnbaum, 2012). A true photograph possesses a universal quality that transcends immediate involvement with the subject or events of photographs (Barnbaum, 2012). Photography has surpassed the capacity of all other machines of assertion, all other languages and image-making technologies (Bajorek, 2010), as images are mediations between the world and human beings (Flusser, 1983). While the technological elements of photography influence the photographer and image, Flusser (1983) believes that there is also a magic of photography that allows an eternal return to the world depicted. This magical element is related to the notion of ‘aura’ (Halpern and Humphreys, 2014), where aura defines as an aspect that provokes the object’s transparency and uniqueness (Benjamin, 2001).

According to Frosh (2015), photography theory means casting the photograph as equivalent to a footprint in the sand, a material imprint created by 'contact with the object' where the photograph foregrounds the temporal relation of pastness with the original event. Furthermore, photographs must possess favourable 'composition' where composition is the means of bringing viewers into the photographs and holding their attention long enough to define their own feelings (Barnbaum, 2012). Kress and Leeuwen (2004) acknowledges that visual composition is essential especially in food photography as it refers to the arrangement of elements within the space of a picture and their orientation to the position of the viewer.

Consumer behaviour is the mental, physical and emotional activities that people engage in selecting, purchasing, using and disposing of products and services to satisfy needs and desires (Priest, Carter, & Statt, 2013). Consumer behaviour theory help explain the attitude toward one's overall favourableness or unfavourableness toward performing the behaviour, where Jeffries, Noar, and Thayer (2015) believes that food consumption attitudes have become a powerful indicator of food consumption behaviour. Steenkam (1993) affirms that food consumption is a vehicle for social stratification, an embodiment of class inequality, and of the stratification of knowledge, aesthetic sensibility and values. One example is the consumption of greasy foods which decreases with social class since food choice is predominantly based on their needs while additional desire such as health-related reasons are also of great important for higher-class people (DeGraaf and Stafleu, 1992).

Combining photography theory and consumption behaviour, the inevitable visual exposure to food has been an essential role in consumption behaviour (Spence et al., 2016). Visualisation of food is believed to be a socialization agent that impacts on food consumption intentions through attitudes and cognitions (Jeffries, Noar and Thayer, 2015). For instance, Murphy (2016) found that higher-class people are inclined to capture, collect, and show off their food online as they are able to buy different choices of food based on what they desire. Also,

millennials' dietary practices, consumption and demand for foods are proved to be deeply influenced by visual media exposure (Jeffries, Noar, and Thayer, 2015). This is due to the rise of smartphone photography with apps particularly Instagram that allows users to upload and share photos easily (Halpern and Humphreys, 2014). In fact, Vohs et al (2013) initiated that delaying eating by performing a short 'food photography ritual' (retrieve smartphone, position plate, snap photos, and post) could actually increase food consumption behaviour as it positively influences the perception of the food.

This consumer behaviour of 'Camera Eats First' has turned into a global trend and phenomenon (Lo, 2016). Broyles (2014) argued that food photos are so appealing because people begin each meal by 'eating with their eyes' and sharing a meal photo has become a status symbol that establishes users' social media hierarchy. Dabrowska (2016) found that food photography obsession is known as the second most popular subject of photography fanatics on Instagram currently after the 'selfie' tsunami. Another consumer behaviour is called 'savouring motives'. Caplin and Leahy (2001) clarified that this behaviour emerges where consumers prefer to extend the period in which they can savour an enjoyable prize. Coary and Poor (2016) also analysed that food photography increases the savouring associated with consumption, where it increases attitudes and taste evaluations of the experience when consumption actually takes place. Furthermore, Schüssler et al. (2012)'s study claims that visual exposure to food tend to influence eating behaviour and just looking at food pictures may be enough to cause an increase in ghrelin, a hormone that causes hunger.

Therefore, the first objective is to examine the link between food photography on Instagram and food consumption behaviour of 18-29-year olds.

2.3. MOTIVATIONS BEHIND THE FOODIE CULTURE ON SOCIAL MEDIA

Motivation is a theoretical construct used to describe behaviour (Makki and Abid, 2017). A person who feels no inspiration to act is characterized as unmotivated whereas someone who is energized toward an end is considered motivated (Ryan and Deci, 2000a). Psychologists have posited two main types of motivation: intrinsic and extrinsic (Reiss, 2012). Firstly, intrinsic motivation is most commonly defined as ‘doing something for its own sake’ and purely based on self-satisfaction (Reiss, 2012), which aligns with self-identity theory that refers to ‘me’ versus ‘not me’ categorizations (Leonardelli and Toh, 2015). Secondly, extrinsic motivation pertains to a wide variety of behaviours where the motivation for action extends beyond those inherent in the activity itself (Guay, Vallerand, and Blanchard, 2000). This is consistent with social identity theory where individuals define their sense of self in terms of social categories or group memberships (Tajfel and Turner, 1979).

2.3.1. INTRINSIC MOTIVATION: SELF-IDENTITY THEORY

According to Guay, Vallerand and Blanchard (2000), intrinsic motivation refers to performing an activity for itself, in order to experience pleasure and satisfaction inherent in the activity. Waterman (2004) proposed that intrinsic motivation serves as the defining dimension of self-identity theory, along with ‘feelings of personal expressiveness’. For instance, people with an overweening interest in food have been expressing themselves as ‘foodies’ (Poole, 2012). According to Zycherman (2014), the term ‘foodie’ is a global identifier of someone who is interested in food beyond the daily practices of eating and cooking, that has developed a substantial self-identity applied in today’s generation. Foodies view food as a type of art that has a deep personal meaning that could shape individuals’ identities (Ginsberg, 2015). Sirgy (1982) also interpreted that consumption of a food brand is often congruent with self-image that an individual want to portray. Moreover, Hanspal and Devasagayam (2017) believe that consumption symbolizes the personality and lifestyle of consumers that often help in

expressing social distinction. In fact, not only do consumers want to show their ‘authentic’ dining experience, these food photographs function as digital self-representation, social belonging simulation, and reinforcement of social class norms (Herman, 2017).

The identity of a person exists in past, present and future time frames where identity is a conscious or intuitive sense of sameness over time (Horowitz, 2012). The effect of self-identity should strengthen because repeated performance of a behaviour increases both the likelihood that the behaviour is an important component of the self-identity and the person’s motivation to validate their status as a role member (Terry, Hogg and White, 1999). Interestingly, the link between self-identity and behavioural intentions (a person’s perceived likelihood to engage in a given behaviour) is not only conceived as a distinct psychological self-entity but also social identity (Terry, Hogg and White, 1999). As social identity serves as an extrinsic motivation (Baay, 2014), there are some overlap between these two motivations which will be explained in section 2.3.3.

2.3.2. EXTRINSIC MOTIVATION: SOCIAL IDENTITY THEORY

Extrinsic motivation refers to an activity of gaining a desired outcome, where motivation arises from outside the individual (Makki and Abid, 2017). Social identity theory is considered part of extrinsic motivation that refers to external factors affecting the individual’s behaviour (Antonioli et al., 2016). In contrast with self-identity theory, a social identity is a person’s knowledge that he or she belongs to a common social identification as members of the same social category (Stets and Burke, 2000). According to Hogg and Vaughan (2018), social identity theory is the theory of intergroup relation based on self-categorization, social comparison and the construction of a shared self-definition in terms of ingroup-defining properties. Through communicating with others, individuals express their belonging to various groups, assess group image and reputation (Dutton, Dukerich and Harquail, 1994).

Unlike the intrinsic motivation, photos serve as a way to ‘share’ food with others (Broyles, 2014), where watching the ‘likes and comments’ give an uplifting virtual-sharing experience and to ‘feel even better’ (Hall, 2016). Furthermore, Greenfield (2014) found that the ability to go out and get a nicely presented meal has become more obtainable due to the eagerness of ‘showing off to friends’. Additionally, *Harpers & Queen*, the British style magazine, referred to *foodies* as ‘cuisine poseurs’ who perceived sophisticated culinary consumption as a means of social distinction (Solier, 2013). Thus, it is undeniable that people take photos of their food not only for themselves, but to assess group image and reputation (Greenfield, 2014). In contrast with self-identity theory embedded in intrinsic motivation, the urge to *foodstagram* extends far beyond a simple desire to share experience but involves a complex process of self-branding and identity in defining the self (Herman, 2017). As reported by Ryan and Deci (2000b), extrinsic motivation is an activity that is done to attain some separable outcomes beyond the activity itself.

Interestingly, Sledgianowski and Kulviwat (2009) indicates that both types of motivations (intrinsic and extrinsic) are dominant predictors of food photography, discussed in the following section.

2.3.3. INTRINSIC VERSUS EXTRINSIC MOTIVATION

Intrinsic and extrinsic motivations are often certified to work in opposite directions (Antonioli et al., 2016). Firstly, in terms of self-identity theory (intrinsic motivation), Sledgianowski and Kulviwat (2009) indicate that intrinsic motivations such as self-satisfaction and enjoyment play a bigger role in the behaviour of social media usage. The concept of self-satisfaction itself defines as the totality of the individual’s perceptions and quality of life generalized by each individual’s mind (Ilinykh and Udaltsova, 2016). This explains why individuals with foodstagramming rituals are always equipped with their smartphones on the dining table (McNeilly, 2016). Thanarugchok’s (2017) study found that 14 out of 20 college students

perceived posting photos as a hobby or for one's own pleasure which is classified as intrinsic motivations.

In contrast, Westbrook (2016) established that there are four extrinsic drivers embedded in social identity theory that influence the behaviour of foodie: rise of the fashionable status, importance of social media, trend to publicize life to the public, and the view of food as method to express desirable lifestyle. French philosopher and gourmand, Brillat-Savarin (2011) wrote, '*tell me what you eat, and I will tell you what you are*'. Today, people are bounded with extrinsic motivation to show the world what they eat by photographing every meal, to reveal themselves more vividly than by merely reciting the names of appetizers and entrees (Murphy, 2010).

Nevertheless, some authors identified situations where two types of motivations may be complementary and reinforce each other (Antonioli et al., 2016). For instance, Thanarugchok's (2017) study of 20 college students with the mean age of 21 also found that self-satisfaction (intrinsic motivation) and seeking fame or positive feedback (extrinsic motivation) are two major factors that concurrently drive food photography on Instagram. Furthermore, 360i Digital Agency (2011) proved that both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation are equally important. The study determined that a quarter of food photos are motivated by intrinsic motivation of publishing a 'food diary' for own pleasure. Another major motivation is to expose a self-created dish that involves egotistical-related extrinsic motivation, to show off their creations, efforts and eventually seek approval or credits by others (360i Digital Agency, 2011).

Therefore, the second objective aims to explore which type of motivation influences 18-29 years old's enthusiasm of posting food photography on Instagram.

2.4. FOOD PHOTOGRAPHY AND CULTURAL DIMENSIONS

Food is not just something to enjoy and give nourishment but also a powerful tool through which can be viewed to understand other cultures (Cox, 2017). Predominantly, this section will explore the global trend from various different countries, focusing on both the eastern and western values. The theory of Hofstede's cultural dimensions constitutes a paradigm of cultural differences across cross-cultural domain, which was created by Geert Hofstede from 1970 (Minkov and Hofstede, 2011). According to Hofstede's Insights (2018a), there are six dimensions of Hofstede cultural dimensions which are: Power Distance, Uncertainty Avoidance, Individualism versus Collectivism (I-C), Masculinity versus Femininity (MAS), Long-term Orientation versus Short-term Normative Orientation (LTO) and Indulgence versus Restraint (IND-R).

According to Fang et al (2016), individualism and indulgence cultures are closely related which means that country with high individualism tend to have a positive correlation with being indulgence. Thus, although all the dimensions are essential, only two applicable dimensions of I-C and IND-R are chosen in this study and will be discussed further.

FIRST DIMENSION: INDIVIDUALISM – COLLECTIVISM CULTURES

The first dimension is I-C, where 'individualism' is defined as a situation in which people are supposed to look after themselves and their immediate family only, whereas 'collectivism' is a situation in which people belong to in-groups are supposed to look after them in exchange for loyalty (Hofstede and Bond, 1984). In-group collectivism refers to a strong sense of embeddedness construct through collaboration, harmony and interdependence within the in-group (Gupta and Kirwan, 2013). In individualistic cultures, one's identity is in the person while in collectivistic cultures, people are 'we' - conscious (Goodrich and de Mooij, 2013). The typical collectivistic societies are those within the Eastern world such as East Asia and Middle

Eastern or Arabian countries while the roots of individualism tend to be within the Western world (Darwish and Huber, 2003).

People in individualism cultures are autonomous and give priority to their personal goals over the goals of others (Triandis, 2001). They tend to engage in self-promotion than self-effacement and value pride over modesty (Jackson and Wang, 2013). In individualistic cultures, food photography is seen as personal enjoyment, self-interest and pleasure (Lai, 2011). The desire of food photography is initially drawn as a way of documenting personal life, which then lead to self-expression rather than social needs and belongings (Laurent, 2017). Thus, unlike collectivistic cultures, people in individualist cultures tend to resist social pressure that contradicts with their own values and preferences (Goncalo and Staw, 2006), leading them to be more consistent and persistent in food photography. Waters and Lo (2012) concludes that they tend to be more consumed in social media due to high engagement in multiple in-groups, leading to permeable boundaries.

In contrast, people in collectivism cultures are interdependent, behave in a communal way and are especially concerned with relationships (Triandis, 2001). Dadgar, Vithayathil and Osiri (2017) found that higher levels of collectivism predict lower levels of social media usage since they prefer in-person communications and socializing in the real world over the digital world. In high collectivist cultures, users tend to focus more on the community that they belong (Garcia-Gavilanes, Quercia and Jaimes, 2013) and believe that the 'real-life' relationship is more important than online relationship (Al-Kandari, Al-Sumair and Al-Hunaiyyan, 2017). According to Chang (2015), food photography in collectivist culture is seen as bringing people together and connects people from different countries to share their experience and opinions. 360i Digital Agency (2011) also determine that collectivist consumers share food photos due to communal reasons of special occasion that bring people together in one place and must be well documented.

SECOND DIMENSION: INDULGENCE – RESTRAINT CULTURES

IND-R is related to the gratification versus control of basic human desires related to enjoying life, where *Figure 2.1* listed several differences of societies within this dimension (Hofstede, 2011). IND-R dimension was added in 2010 that was based in part on Michael Minkov research, creator of the extensive World Values Survey (Hofstede, 2015). According to Ismail and Lu (2014), this dimension refers to ‘happiness values’ where indulgence stands for free gratification society while restraint refers to society with strict social norms and high gratification control. Thus, countries with high indulgence tend to promote creativity and emphasize strong individualism due to looser knots among individuals and less structured environment (Fang et al., 2016).

Figure 2.1: Differences between Indulgence and Restrained Societies:

Indulgence	Restrained
Higher percentage of people declaring themselves very happy	Fewer very happy people
A perception of personal life control	A perception of helplessness: what happens to me is not my own doing
Freedom of speech seen as important	Freedom of speech is not a primary concern
Higher importance of leisure	Lower importance of leisure
More likely to remember positive emotions	Less likely to remember positive emotions
In countries with educated populations, higher birthrates	In countries with educated populations, lower birthrates
More people actively involved in sports	Fewer people actively involved in sports
In countries with enough food, higher percentages of obese people	In countries with enough food, fewer obese people
In wealthy countries, lenient sexual norms	In wealthy countries, stricter sexual norms
Maintaining order in the nation is not given a high priority	Higher number of police officers per 100,000 population

(Source: Hofstede, 2011)

In contrast, restrained society has a tendency of cynicism and pessimism as individual actions are restrained by strict social norms (Nurunnabi, 2017). Thus, it is possible to characterize high-indulgent societies as optimist (Yildirim and Barutçu, 2016). Furthermore, the feeling of optimism in indulgent societies decreases cynicism and creates the basis of trust as there is a belief that Internet is a trustworthy platform for building markets and communities (Jøsang,

2007). The online trust ensured by optimism then has a significant role in online environment that led to a positive attitude and willingness to involve in social media, specifically Instagram (Yildirim, Arslan, and Barutçu, 2016). Hence, in relation to food photography, indulgence countries such as the US, post more food photos compared to the restrained countries due to high freedom of speech (Hofstede, 2011). Consistent with the statistics shown in *Figure 2.2*, US has become the topmost country with the highest Instagram users.

Figure 2.2: Top 10 countries based on number of Instagram users as of April 2018

(Source: Statista, 2018a)

Since several studies found that countries with high indulgence tend to emphasize high individualism, *the third objective aims to prove whether a high level of indulgence and individualism culture tend to involve consumers more in food photography compared to the restraint and collectivism cultures.* Finally, after analysing all the three objectives simultaneously, *the final objective is to provide recommendations for the food industry on*

how to engage more efficiently with the rise of social media and consumption behaviour in the future (discussed in section 5.2).

2.5. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this chapter certified that visual exposure to food has been an essential role in consumption behaviour, leading the first objective to examine the link between food photography on Instagram and food consumption behaviour. After analysing the theory of self-identity and social identity and two types of motivations (intrinsic and extrinsic) embedded within food photography behaviour, the second objective aims to explore which type of motivation influences the enthusiasm of posting food photography on Instagram. Consistent with the third objective, this chapter found that the combination of two Hofstede dimensions (individualism-collectivism and indulgence-restraint cultures) are highly applicable for food photography investigation worldwide. The next chapter will explain how this research will be performed and carried out.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.1. INTRODUCTION

This chapter will explain a suitable methodology to achieve the paper's aim and objectives. Starting with a brief explanation of research philosophy, approach and method. Followed with qualitative data collection employed and interview process. Sampling methods and qualitative data analysis will also be evaluated. Finally, ethical considerations throughout the research are discussed.

3.2. RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY

Research philosophy is a belief in which data about a phenomenon should be gathered, analysed and used (Lehaney and Vinten, 1994). In terms of philosophical perspective, interpretivism (or interpretivist) paradigm is chosen since the interviewer attempts to understand the phenomenon of food photography through the identity that the participants have assigned to themselves (Myers, 2013). Moreover, interpretive research is guided by the researcher's set of beliefs and feelings (Levers, 2013) and focuses primarily on recognizing the meaning of participants' experiences and actions (Fossey et al., 2002).

3.3. RESEARCH APPROACH

Consistent with the interpretivism philosophy, an inductive approach is applied based on the observation of empirical reality (Collis and Hussey, 2009). Although this paper will be using previous theories within the initial data analysis, inductive approach is mainly employed throughout the research¹. Hyde (2000) believes that most qualitative research follows an

¹ Has been discussed and approved by the supervisor

inductive process to suit the investigation areas where the concepts under study are less developed (i.e. food photography on Instagram).

3.4. RESEARCH METHOD

This paper focuses on qualitative research method as it offers a rich description of complex phenomena (Sofaer, 1999) and emphasizes an inductive approach to the relationship between theory and research (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Similarly, Dey (1993) believes that qualitative method is best in explaining important reality and relationships in a meaningful way. Throughout Chapter 4, the researcher uses numerical data to explain the findings of the research. This is called ‘quasi-statistics’ (Maxwell, 2010). This is utilized to adequately present the amount of evidence in the data and identify patterns that are not apparent without numerical data. Maxwell (2010) argues that the use of numbers by itself doesn’t make a study ‘mixed methods’ which means that this paper is purely a qualitative research.

However, qualitative method is not without its weakness due to the nature of ambiguity (Atieno, 2009). Qualitative research is also often difficult to replicate as it is unstructured and reliant upon the researcher’s ingenuity (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Nevertheless, Hammarberg, Kirkman and Lacey (2016) argued that qualitative research techniques, especially semi-structured interview is the best approach to seek views on a focused topic as they are able to answer questions about experience, meaning and perspectives. Moreover, there has been recent enthusiasm for the use of visual methods in qualitative research (Barbour, 2014), as they are able to generate another dimension and insights into the everyday world (Glaw et al., 2017). Therefore, both qualitative and visual methods are selected due to its ability to analyse information conveyed through language and behaviour (Berkwits and Inui, 1998).

3.5. QUALITATIVE DATA COLLECTION

Since the nature of this paper involves the exploration of consumer behaviours, the qualitative combination of semi-structured interview and photo-elicitation is used to address customers' insights in detail.

3.5.1. SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW

Semi-structured interviews are a type of interviews that involves comprehensive conversations prompted by the research aim, but are strongly open to interviewee's perceptions, opinions, and experiences (Cridland et al., 2016). Myers (2013) states that this approach gives safe guidelines for the interviewer yet allowing some improvisation from both interviewer and the participants. Specifically, the open-endedness allows participants to contribute detailed information while advocating the interviewer to ask probing questions as a means of follow-up (Turner, 2010).

However, semi-structured interviews may lead to inconsistency as questions and results explored might differ from one respondent to another (Collis and Hussey, 2009). Thus, it is difficult to directly compare the results since each interview is unique. Nevertheless, this approach provides more detailed information than other methods while also providing a more relaxed atmosphere for both the interviewer and respondents (Boyce and Neale, 2006). Most importantly, semi-structured interviews with open-ended questions is chosen as it captures the best of both approaches: unstructured and fully-structured interview (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

3.5.2. PHOTO-ELICITATION METHOD

Bryman and Bell (2011) argue that the use of visual techniques could stimulate creative thinking, problem solving and gather subjective elements. Visual representation is a staple of the behavioural sciences (Stanczak, 2007), that interpret the world through the sense of sight (Pole, 2004). In this study, the photo-elicitation method (PEM) is selected, a type of visual

method that involves in evaluating photographs during the interview (Bridger, 2013). PEM allows researcher to build rapport with the respondents (Meo, 2010) and accumulates unforeseen meanings that would have otherwise been dormant (Bridger,2013).

However, there are several inconsistencies of visual methods implied by the phrase ‘the camera cannot lie’ (Cudlipp, 1992), where participants can or often lie when delivering the meanings (Loizos, 2000). Nevertheless, using PEM in a flexible manner could allow the researcher to ‘think on her/his feet’ where the key success is to be actively involved in eliciting information during the conversation (Barbour, 2014). Thus, together with remarkably engaging interview questions or prompts (Sheridan, Chamberlain, and Dupuis, 2011) and perpetual attention given to the discussion (Wood, 2006), PEM is a legitimate method elected in this study.

3.6. INTERVIEW PROCESS

3.6.1. BEFORE THE INTERVIEW: INTRODUCTION

Firstly, the researcher prepared several questions beforehand, grouped them into themes and dress appropriately. The interview begins with a group of questions to tackle each theme which is available in Appendix A. Moreover, a minimum 2 days before the interview, participants submitted 5 different food photographs taken by themselves that have been posted or intended to put on Instagram (either story or post). The interview was formulated with language that is easy to understand by the interviewees. In this stage, interviewees were given a consent form, to state agreement to participate in the interview (See Appendix B). Furthermore, the researcher gathered information of general (i.e. name, age, gender) and specific kind (i.e. social media familiarity), since Bryman and Bell (2011) argued that such information is useful for contextualising the interviewee’s answers.

3.6.2. DURING THE INTERVIEW: CONVERSATION AND QUESTIONS

Essentially, open-ended questions beginning with *who, what, why, where, when and how* were mainly used (Myers, 2013). To avoid confusion, all the photographs were numbered so that the participant and interviewer knows which photo is being referred to. Adopted from Kvale (1996), several types of questions; introductory, follow-up, structuring, specifying and interpreting questions were selected throughout the interview (purpose of each question is depicted in Appendix C). Furthermore, rather than continually firing off questions, silence by allowing several pauses is constantly exploited to give opportunity for interviewees to amplify their answers (Kvale, 1996).

3.6.3. AFTER THE INTERVIEW: CONCLUSION

After thanking respondents for their valuable time, the interviewer also made secondary notes on how the interview went (i.e. all Interviewees are open, cooperative and well-dressed), where the interview took place, and any other feelings of the interview. The whole interviews were recorded with a smartphone audio recording since it is convenient, easy to use and highly portable. All the interviews were then manually transcribed and stored in the researcher's personal computer immediately after each interview to obtain fresh results.

3.7. SAMPLING METHODS

Curtis et al (2000) argued that the right sampling strategy should be relevant to the aim and objectives of the research to generate rich information of the phenomena. Thus, convenience sampling is implemented as it is affordable and accessible to the researcher. It is a type of non-random sampling where members meet certain practical criteria such as easy accessibility, geographical proximity, available at a given time, and willingness to participate are included for the study purpose (Etikan, Musa, and Alkassim, 2016). In terms of sample size, Alhabash and Ma (2017) found that young adults (aged 18-29 years) have the highest social media

adoption rates (90%) compared to the other age groups. *Figure 3.1* also shows that the age group of 18-24 and 25-34 are the highest Instagram users worldwide. Additionally, more than just sharing pictures of food, the creation of food blogs, food forums and food apps has strengthened the relationship between social media and food (Endres, 2016). Thus, the age group of 18-29 is chosen since they are most in touch with social media and active in food photography. This purposive sampling technique is the strategy applied to exercise the judgement of who will provide the best perspective on the phenomenon of interest, and then intentionally invites those specific perspective into the study (Abrams, 2010).

According to Dworkin (2012), determining an adequate sample size in qualitative research is based on the goal of the research objectives and ability to reach redundancy across relevant characteristics and concepts intended. Thus, there are eight participants chosen from eight different countries ranged from 18-29 years, which is consistent with the research paper objectives.

Figure 3.1. Distribution of Instagram Users Worldwide as of April 2018 (by Age and Gender):

(Source: Statista, 2018b)

3.8. QUALITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS

Thematic analysis is an analytical approach employed in analysing both implicit and explicit ideas through themes that captures the complexities of meaning within a textual data (Guest, MacQueen and Namey, 2012). The most apparent benefit of thematic analysis is that it can be utilized to interpret various research aspects (Braun and Clarke, 2006) while providing a rich and detailed information (Nowell et al., 2017). Throughout the analysis, the researcher takes an active role in selecting and categorising the data into themes (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Adopted from Braun and Clarke (2006), there are six phases of thematic analysis conducted:

3.8.1. DATA FAMILIARISATION

Firstly, to be familiar with the data, all the interviews were transcribed into written form so that it could be studied in detail, linked with analytic notes and codes (Bailey, 2008). Although all the transcribing interviews were eminently time-consuming, Braun and Clarke (2006) argued that time spent in transcription develops deep understanding and data familiarity to the researcher.

3.8.2. INITIAL CODES GENERALISATION

According to Guest, MacQueen and Namey (2012), coding has become an integral part of the analysis since it helps qualitative analyst to link specific codes to the generated themes. In this stage, the interviewer circled both key and repeated words on the transcript and then generated the code explanation based on the line number extracted from the transcript (See Appendix D).

3.8.3. SEARCHING FOR THEMES

The researcher has grouped the interview questions based on the rough themes generated before the interview. Thus, grouping different codes into potential themes has become quicker and easier. According to Braun and Clarke (2006), this technique simplifies the collation of all the relevant codes within the identified themes. Based on the code generated, visual representations were constructed to depict the identification of relevant themes (See Appendix E).

3.8.4. REVIEWING THEMES

The researcher integrated ‘social media importance’ and ‘food industry on social media’ into ‘the importance of social media for food industry’ theme since most of the participants have closely link their social media behaviour and their actual dining options, leading to some data overlapping. Due to high association between two themes, ‘dual criteria’ has been merged to reflect the entire data set meaningfully (Braun and Clark, 2006).

3.8.5. DEFINING AND NAMING THEMES

According to Braun and Clarke (2006), this stage involves in delivering concise definitions to give the reader a clear understanding about the themes created, depicted in *Table 3.1*.

Table 3.1: final themes and definitions generated

Themes	Definition
1. Connection Between Food Photography on Instagram and Consumption Behaviour	A relationship in which food photography on Instagram is linked with food consumption behaviour
2. Motivation Behind Posting Food Photography on Instagram	Reasons for food photography behaviour and posting food photos on Instagram
3. The Cultural Impact of Food Photography	The social behaviour of a particular country that has an impact of food photography
4. The Importance of Social Media for Food Industry	The significant value of social media in thriving communication with consumers within food industry

3.8.6. PRODUCING THE TEXT ANALYSIS

Once all the final themes are formulated, the researcher then produce a deep explanation of each themes constructed, which is discussed in chapter four.

3.9. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Ethical issues are present especially in qualitative research due to the subtle nature compared to other research methods (Orb, Eisenhauer and Wynaden, 2001). This research paper has completed the required ethical procedures stipulated by TYMS, where all files (transcribed interview and audio) are held securely in password-protected files to secure participants' confidentiality.

3.9.1. ANONYMITY AND CONFIDENTIALITY

Firstly, ignoring participants' anonymity and confidentiality is terribly unethical (Kumar, 2011). However, Pink (2012) acknowledges that it is often impractical or even illogical to maintain the anonymity and confidentiality of photographs. Visual methods such as PEM is justified to reveal information that text-based methods cannot, enable participants to present particular aspects of their identities, where altering visual material by 'disguising' participants may destroy the very purpose of producing data visually (Clark, 2012). Nevertheless, the researcher has anonymised all participant's name by creating pseudonyms and spent an extra effort to assure all the interview content and photos are confidential through a detailed informed consent (See Appendix B) that was explained thoroughly before the interview (Meo, 2010).

3.9.2. INFORMED CONSENT

Informed consent is a central principle in ethical research and is no less central to visual research than other types of research (Wiles et al., 2008). Thus, a consent form is used throughout this research which is shown in Appendix B. However, Clark, Prosser and Wiles (2010) found that obtaining informed consent is less straightforward in visual research since it is not always clear whether participants fully understand what are they consenting to. Thus, throughout the interview, the researcher has genuinely attempt to put participants at ease through helpfulness of immediate barriers and friendliness, leading participants to be fully aware of what they are comply for.

3.9.3. SUBJECTIVITY

Subjectivity is a way of thinking that is conditioned by educational background, experience and skills (Kumar, 2011). Based on Matteucci (2013), photographic images often convey multiple subjective meanings that always be interpreted differently. To encounter this, the distinction of researcher' subjective processes to objectively study the psychology of subjects

(Ratner, 2002) is clearly emphasised. For instance, several prompting questions such as ‘*when do you say symbolic, what does it really means to you?*’ were asked with full subjectivity awareness to gain the purest respondent perspective (Qu and Dumay, 2011).

3.10. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, interpretivism was selected as the appropriate research philosophy for this study together with an inductive qualitative approach using the combination of semi-structured interview and photo-elicitation method. A comprehensive interview process consisted of three stages is then reported, where the critical explanation of thematic analysis is developed. Throughout the research, the appropriate number of sample size and ethical considerations are considered to investigate the paper objectives. The next chapter will present the findings and discussions of the data.

CHAPTER FOUR: FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. INTRODUCTION

This section will present the key results from the primary data combination of semi-structured interview and photo-elicitation method. The following findings are based on the four research objectives, where the discussions are closely associated with the key areas found in the literature review. There are eight participants in this study and all participants have provided valuable results for each research objective.

4.2. FINDINGS

Table 4.1. shows the respondents profile including name, age, gender, nationality and occupation. It also shows the interview information including the length of the interview, where the interview was conducted and the date of interview.

No.	Name	Age	Gender	Nationality	Occupation	Interview Length	Interview Location	Interview Date
1.	Deniz	24	Female	Turkey	Student	23:58 mins	JB Morrel Library	5 July 2018
2.	Soha	23	Female	India	Student	23: 24 mins	JB Morrel Library	5 July 2018
3.	Su	28	Female	China	Student	24:50 mins	JB Morrel Library	6 July 2018
4.	Yazmin	29	Female	Mexico	Student	23:41 mins	JB Morrel Library	8 July 2018
5.	Natalie	22	Female	USA	Student	23:02 mins	JB Morrel Library	9 July 2018

6.	Tadd	18	Male	Australia	Student	25:35 mins	Skype	10 July 2018
7.	Mhen	25	Male	Thailand	Student	26:40 mins	JB Morrel Library	12 July 2018
8.	Mitty	21	Female	UK	Student	27:03 mins	JB Morrel Library	13 July 2018

4.3. DISCUSSION

Table 4.2. shows the results summary of 8 participants based on each objective and will be discussed in detail in the following section.

<i>Table 4.2. Results Summary based on 8 participants</i>					
No.	Participants	Objective 1	Objective 2	Objective 3	Objective 4
1.	Deniz (24)	Positive Link	Intrinsic	Proved	Important
2.	Soha (23)	Positive Link	Intrinsic and Extrinsic	Not proven	Important
3.	Su (28)	Positive Link	Intrinsic and Extrinsic	Not proven	Important
4.	Yazmin (29)	Positive Link	Intrinsic and Extrinsic	Not proven	Important
5.	Natalie (22)	No Link	Intrinsic	Proved	Important
6.	Tadd (18)	No Link	Intrinsic and Extrinsic	Proved	Important
7.	Mhen (25)	Positive Link	Extrinsic	Not proven	Important
8.	Mitty (21)	No Link	Intrinsic	Not proven	Important

4.3.1. OBJECTIVE 1: LINK BETWEEN FOOD PHOTOGRAPHY ON INSTAGRAM AND FOOD CONSUMPTION BEHAVIOUR

This section will show whether there is a positive, negative or even no link between food photography on Instagram and food consumption behaviour from each participant. To see the accurate link, this section is divided in several parts:

4.3.1.1. FOOD PHOTOGRAPHY ON INSTAGRAM

As noted by Barnbaum (2012), Bajorek (2010), and Flusser (1983), all the participants chose Instagram as their favourite social media platform. As per Jeffries, Noar and Thayer (2015), all participants were considered as heavy Instagram users as they admitted to opening their Instagram account first thing in the morning. Despite getting more inspirations on Instagram and less advertisement, the main reason for most participants are due to its simplicity and main feature of photo-sharing. Yazmin believes that *'A picture says a thousand words and this is why visualization is important for me'*. Mhen also mentioned that *'I post most of my food photos on Instagram because it's a photo-presentation, rather than information-presentation'*. As presumed by Halpern and Humphreys (2014) regarding Instagram's easiness to share photos, Tadd specified that *'It's easier to share photos on Instagram since people only come to Instagram to see photos, rather than Facebook that are used to share news and stuffs'*. As per Halpern and Humphreys (2014) and Benjamin (2001), Su mentioned that *'I feel like photos are very attractive as it could get 100% of my attention!'*.

4.3.1.2. FOOD PHOTOGRAPHY AND VISUAL EXPOSURE

As per Broyles (2014), Deniz believed that *'For me, taste only is not enough. It should satisfy my eyes first'* (See Picture 4.1). Moreover, although Natalie argued that *'Your eyesight is better than any other things like your smartphone'* she believes that food photography has become an endless phenomenon when she said *'I feel like everyone takes food photo nowadays, so you know what you will expect in 20 years'*. Thus, Lo (2016)'s finding of 'Camera Eats First'

behaviour has been proven and has turned into a global trend. As per Schüssler et al (2012), seeing food posts are found very enticing for some participants where Soha explained that *'When I see my friend with a good cup of coffee on my Instagram feed, I will feel like, yes, I really need them right now! So yeah, looking at my friends' post triggers me a lot!'*. Tadd said that, *'If the food looks really pretty, I usually ask my friends to visit the place immediately!'*. Additionally, Yazmin said that *'Looking at all these foods that my friends posted always seduces me to eat the food even more.'*

Picture 4.1. Deniz: *'taste only is not enough. It should satisfy my eyes first'*

4.3.1.3. FOOD PHOTOGRAPHY AND SAVOURING MOTIVES

Firstly, to investigate this link, participants were asked whether they agree or disagree with the statement by Gander (2017), where US researchers declared that *'the effects of photographing food can make it less enjoyable to eat'*. In fact, six out of eight participants disagree with the statement (See Appendix F). Interestingly, most participants have linked the reason behind food photography with their actual consumption behaviour and enjoyment to eat. For instance, Deniz explained that food photography *'actually makes the food way tastier'*, she continued *'it*

convinces me that the food is good' which is consistent with the study by Caplin and Leahy (2001). Moreover, when asked *'does taking picture somehow triggers you to eat more?'*, Su answered, *'It definitely is! Because if I take photos, I always find the best angle of the photo and don't let me start with the editing!'*. As per Coary and Poor (2016), Mhen explained, *'I will not take a photo when the food is ugly! That's why I said presentation is really good because it could attract you to enjoy your food more'*.

OBJECTIVE 1 CONCLUSION

The study found that three out of eight participants argued that there is no link between food photographing and consumption behaviour. For instance, Mitty argued that *'It's two different, unrelated actions'* and Natalie with *'I don't think taking photos before I eat would influence my enjoyment to eat'*. This has contradicted with Vohs et al (2013)'s study, where performing 'food photography ritual' will always increase food consumption behaviour. However, five out of eight participants believe that there is a positive relationship between food photography and their actual consumption behaviour (See Appendix G). After analysing the power of food photography on Instagram, importance of visual exposure and a clear connection between food photography and savouring motives, as per Coary and Poor (2016) and Schüssler at al (2012), it is appropriate to claim **that in terms of objective 1, there is a positive link between food photography on Instagram and food consumption behaviour between 18-29 years old.**

4.3.2. OBJECTIVE 2: TYPE OF MOTIVATION THAT MAINLY INFLUENCES POSTING FOOD PHOTOGRAPHY ON INSTAGRAM

This section will discuss which type of motivation that mainly influences posting food photography on Instagram. To find the accurate type of motivation, this section has classified each participant responses into two sections: intrinsic and extrinsic motivation.

4.3.2.1. INTRINSIC MOTIVATION

The results of the interviews revealed that three out of eight participants are influenced by only intrinsic motivation and four out of eight participants are jointly influenced alongside extrinsic motivation, where the key responses are given in Appendix H.

As per Sledgianowski and Kulviwat (2009), it is proven that self-enjoyment is the main reason for posting food photography on Instagram. For instance, Deniz was aware that food photo will always give her less likes but still posting due to her own personal expressiveness of ‘*enjoying the moment*’ (See Appendix H). Soha also argued perceived food photography as a ‘souvenir’ (See *Picture 4.2*) as a remembrance of special moments, which resembles Waterman (2004)’s study. Similarly, both Su and Yazmin mentioned that their food photography behaviour is partly influenced by the intrinsic motivation of memories shared with friends (See Appendix H). Another important intrinsic motivation influence is when Tadd noted that self-satisfaction has become a major influence of his behaviour (See Appendix H). These findings are parallel with Reiss (2012), where intrinsic motivation is most commonly defined as ‘doing something for its own sake’ and purely based on self-satisfaction.

Picture 4.2. Soha: ‘Food photography is like a ‘souvenir’ for me’

As per Ginsberg (2015), foodies view food as personal meaning and individual identities, that is parallel with Natalie's response, *'I wouldn't post it for people actually. Like for example, I love posting fruit photos on Instagram simply because it motivates me to keep eating healthy. Not every meal has to be big in portions and topping to become an insta-worthy photo!'*. Hence, Natalie is clearly using her platform to maintain the identity of a healthy eater. This behaviour is closely correlated with self-determination theory (SDT) which is an empirically derived theory of human intrinsic motivation and personality without influence from other people or situations (Ryan and Deci, 2000a).

When asked regarding the main reason of posting food photography on Instagram, Mitty answered, *'It was more for the sake of just keeping it on my own accountability, rather than for other people to see it'*. This is consistent with the intrinsic motivation definition that refers to performing activity for itself (Guay, Vallerand and Blanchard, 2000) rather than in terms of social categories or group memberships (Tajfel and Turner, 1979). Similar with 360i Digital Agency (2011)'s findings, Mitty also treated her Instagram posts as her 'virtual diary' (See *Picture 4.3*), which simulates to Herman (2017) study, where culinary posts often function as digital representation, social belonging simulation, and reinforcement of social class norms.

Picture 4.3. Mitty: 'it's more like my virtual diary rather than for other people to see it'

4.3.2.2. EXTRINSIC MOTIVATION

The results of the interview revealed that one out of eight participants is influenced by only extrinsic motivation, and four out of eight participants are partially influenced by extrinsic motivation, alongside intrinsic motivation, where the key responses are given in Appendix I. As per Hall (2016), when is always expecting likes and the more likes he gets, the better he feels (See Appendix I). Moreover, Su directly answered with the connotation '*Of course! Who doesn't?*', when probe whether she cares about the likes she gets. She also mentioned that '*I'm good with taking photos and I exactly know how to take a good one, I think, this is just how Instagram works!*'. Su's response corresponds with Stets and Burke (2000), where belonging in a common social identification is the main influence of her food photography behaviour. Furthermore, Su argued that '*I took so much effort for my photos especially when editing it, I want people to appreciate it!*'. This shows that motivation mainly comes from influences outside of the individual, which is consistent with Makki and Abid (2017)'s study. Similarly, the participant is actively seeking for positive feedback, which supports the study by Thanarugchok (2017).

Yazmin, on the other hand, doesn't really care about the likes but the comments. She is eminently interested with people's opinion and immensely perceived engagement with them (See Appendix I). Yazmin's response coincides with Broyles (2014), where she perceives photos as a way to 'share' food with others. Another theory to explain this motivation is called 'social interactions' which builds upon Prahalad and Ramaswamy (2004)'s model of social engagement theory (SME). Social interactions are defined as the communication among users through social media by fostering a personalized relationship as a transparent means of communication (Gangi and Wasko, 2016). Jensen and Aanestad (2007) also argue that social interactions guide the user in evaluation of how intensely involved they wish to be.

Furthermore, the role of hashtag (a word phrases preceded by a hash sign # operated on Instagram) is not only instrumental in defining self-branding and identity in food (Herman, 2017) but also engagement with others. When questioned about the familiarity and reasons of using hashtags, Mhen answered, ‘*I want people from all over the world to see my picture!*’. Essentially, Tadd said that ‘*I used hashtags to get more engagement with my followers and friends!*’ (See *Picture 4.4*). Moreover, Tadd implied, ‘*Obviously if I go to a fancy restaurant or fine dining, I will always take pictures and post it on Instagram*’, which indicates that he wants to show others what he eats to reveal himself more vividly as a sophisticated eater (Murphy, 2010).

Picture 4.4. Tadd: ‘you want to stay related with others, that’s what hashtags are for’

Additionally, as noted by Westbrook (2016), another extrinsic driver that is embedded in Mhen’s behaviour are the rise of the fashionable status as a foodie and a method to express desirable lifestyle. This is connoted with the statement ‘*in places like Bettys*’ (See Appendix I) which is considered as one of the most high-end cafés in North Yorkshire (*Picture 4.5* below).

Picture 4.5: Mhen: 'you have to take picture, because if not, what's the point?'

In terms of social identity theory, when asked 'do you always put your food photos on Instagram?' (See Appendix A), Su mentioned that 'Always, it's either a story or a post, this is because I want people to think that I am in the good stage of life'. Thus, this behaviour is closely linked with the theory by Hogg and Vaughan (2018) where social comparison plays an important role in the construction of the in-group. Soha also concluded that her platform is favoured as a 'showcase for everyone to see it'. She continued, 'it is kind of hard to tell everyone what you are been up to, but thanks to Instagram to make it happens!' which is clearly corresponds with Terry, Hogg and White (1999)'s study where behavioural intentions are desperately influenced by the validation of social identity.

OBJECTIVE 2 CONCLUSION

After analysing both motivations thoroughly, the study found that half of the respondents have been influenced by both intrinsic and extrinsic motivations. This finding is consistent with Sledgianowski and Kulviwat (2009)'s study where both types of motivations are demonstrated to be dominant predictors of food photography. **Thus, objective 2 established that both**

intrinsic and extrinsic motivations mainly influences 18-29-year olds foodie's enthusiasm of posting food photography on Instagram.

4.3.3. OBJECTIVE 3: A PERSON WITH HIGH LEVEL OF INDULGENCE AND INDIVIDUALISM CULTURE TEND TO INVOLVE MORE IN FOOD PHOTOGRAPHY COMPARED TO AN INDIVIDUAL OF RESTRAIN AND COLLECTIVISM CULTURE

This section questions whether a person with high level of indulgence and individualism culture tend to involve more in food photography compared to an individual of restraint and collectivism culture based on each participants' responses. In order to achieve an accurate result, this section is divided into several classifications based on the nationality of each participant:

4.3.3.1. INDIVIDUALISM AND INDULGENCE CULTURES

There are three participants that are classified within the individualism and indulgence cultures in this study, with two of them showing that individuals with high level of indulgence and individualism culture tend to post more food photography on Instagram (See Appendix J).

In terms of individualism, when inquired about the main reason of posting food photography on Instagram, Mitty explained that *'It is a good way of editing skill and I often just keep some photos on my personal computer'*. When questioned about likes or comments expectations, Nicole answered, *'Well it doesn't really matter, it's my platform, I post stuffs that I like, it's like the way of telling them (followers) that'*. Based on these responses, as found by Triandis (2001), it is proved that a person that is involved in individualism culture tend to give priority to their personal goals over the goals of others. As per Goncalo and Staw (2006), Nicole's response signifies that she prioritizes her own values and preferences rather than social pressure. Furthermore, Tadd argued that *'I post because I want to show people where I eat, in which place, especially if I'm in an exclusive restaurants'* (See Picture 4.6). This has aligned

with the study by Jackson and Wang (2013), where individualistic individual tends to engage more in self-promotion that value pride over modesty.

Picture 4.6: Tadd: *'taken on the top floor of Sydney harbour, my favourite photo so far!'*

In terms of food photography, it is unsurprising to find that all the participants take at least three photos of each meal before consuming their food. When asked *'How often do you take pictures before you eat?'* (See Appendix A), Natalie responded, *'I feel like I take it every time I had a special meal or dish that kind of have a special meaning for me'*. Tadd answered, *'All the time! Although I don't post it every time like I used to, keeping them just makes me happy and satisfied'*. These responses are aligned with Lai (2011)'s finding where food photography is perceived as personal enjoyment, self-interest and pleasure. Persistently, Mitty treats her platform as a *'virtual diary'* and food photography as her *'own accountability'* (See Appendix H). This shows that the desired behind food photography is initially drawn of documenting

personal life rather than social I needs or belongings, which consistent with Carless (2018)'s study.

In terms of trust, Natalie mentioned that '*Social media is a reliable platform to find a lot of information about trip or travel, in fact, I've made some friends online and met few of them when I travel!*'. Similarly, Mitty mentioned that '*Other than Instagram, having social media such as Twitter is very beneficial for me especially on the industry that I want to work in, I feel like social media nowadays gives you a land of opportunity*'. As per Jøsang (2007), people associated with indulgence culture believe that the Internet is a trustworthy platform for building markets and communities. Hence, the online trust shown by these responses proved to build a positive attitude and willingness to involve more in social media specifically Instagram, as discussed by Yildirim, Arslan, and Barutçu (2016).

As per Hofstede (2011), Natalie realises that the majority of Americans are active with Instagram and said that in developed country like the US, food photography would be 'more involved' (See Appendix J). Tadd also answered, '*At least for us, the Australians, we all take heaps of pictures and that is what we all do*', when questioned whether food photography is a global phenomenon. Thus, as reported by Fang et al. (2016), being relatively free from severely uniform and restrictive social norms have led these individuals to associate themselves more with food photography.

4.3.3.2. COLLECTIVISM AND RESTRAINT CULTURES

There are four participants that are classified within the collectivism and restraint cultures in this study, with three of them failing to prove that individuals with high levels of collectivism and restraint cultures tend to post less food photography on Instagram (See Appendix K). Consistent with Darwish and Huber (2003), Turkey, India, China and Thailand are found to be countries with high collectivism and restraint dimension.

In terms of collectivism, one participant proved that individuals tend to focus more on the community to which they belong which corresponds with the study by Gavilanes, Quercia and James (2013). In fact, while having discussion about why Instagram has been chosen as the sharing platform, Deniz argued that *'My friends told me that you are always eating!'* (See Appendix K), which has led her to involve less in food photography. Since Deniz's behaviour is greatly influenced by the in-group, it is proved that people in collectivistic culture tend to be more 'we'-conscious (Goodrich and de Mooij, 2013). This also shows a tendency towards cynicism and pessimism as individual actions are restraint by strict social norms and opinions that closely link with the restraint dimension (Nurunnabi, 2017). Consistently, Mhen believes that *'The internet can be a very dangerous platform as it is so easy to spread wrong information and rumours nowadays'*. Since there is no trust ensured for the majority of people in restraint cultures, there will be no positive attitude and willingness to involve too deeply in social media such as Instagram, which approves the study by Yildirim, Arslan, and Barutçu (2016).

Although the above findings are particularly true, Soha and Su believe that the presence of 'a group of comfortable people' or 'closest friends' and the 'tray of togetherness' perception (See Appendix K) have led them to be more involved in food photography. This coincides with Chang (2015)'s finding, where collectivist culture perceives food photography as bringing people together. When asked *'What do you think about your friends that Instagram their food when you are having a meal?'* (See Appendix A), Soha replied *'I will join them! I would even*

offer her to take a picture of her with the food!'. Similarly, Su mentioned that 'I feel like everyone takes picture! I sometimes think that it's actually weird if someone doesn't. Especially if it looks so good, why don't you take a picture?' (Picture 4.7 below).

Picture 4.7: Su: 'this is what an insta-worthy milkshake would look like'

Furthermore, when inquired whether food photography is particularly huge in Thailand, Mhen answered *'I think this phenomenon is even bigger compared to here (UK) or other countries'* (See Appendix K). These particular findings are inconsistent with the study by Waters and Lo (2012) and Dadgar, Vithayathil, and Osiri (2017), since the higher level of collectivism is not always associated with the lower level of social media usage. In fact, the study by Ardichvili et al (2006) found that because collectivistic cultures tend to give priority to the goals of the larger group, they tend to be more open and willing to share their knowledge throughout greater platforms such as social media. Thus, based on these responses, high level of collectivism and

restraint behaviour failed to prove in posting less food photography on Instagram and this is where the Hofstede’s criticism takes place (See below).

4.3.3.3. HOFSTEDE CRITICISM

Firstly, there is an inconsistency with the study by Fang et al’s (2016) since individualism and indulgence cultures are not always closely affiliated in every country. According to Hofstede’s Inside (2018b), Mexican culture is considered as a collectivistic society of high ‘in groups’ belonging while has a definite tendency toward indulgence. When asked, ‘*Do you think that your behaviour relates to the country that you are from?*’, the participant eminently disagree with the question with concrete explanation (Table 4.3 below). The particular response of ‘*Now everyone has a smartphone*’, connotes that the participant dissociates the link between her nationality and food photography behaviour. Based on this finding, it is inefficient to classify both cultural dimensions together, since two dimensions are not always associated with each other (individualism and indulgence vs collectivism and restraint).

Participants	Objective 3	Nationality	Key Response
Yazmin	Not proven	Mexico	<i>‘Now everyone has a smartphone! I personally don’t think that I post my food photos based on my country! But if you come to Mexico, all the young people are taking photo before they eat!’</i>

Despite the broad acceptance of Hofstede’s framework, many other researchers have raised critical challenges and Hofstede has even met with fierce opposition (Eringa et al., 2015). Since this paper aims to explore a global phenomenon of food photography, some researchers have claimed that Hofstede’s dimension is too old to be of any modern value, particularly with today’s rapidly changing global environments, internationalization and convergence (Jones,

2007). In fact, globalization has led to mixing up of cultures and no culture entails to its original characteristics. According to Sotshangane (2002), culture is some kind of information that human beings are not born with but can be learned during the long process of education, socialization and interacting with each other in social life. Thus, researchers found that culture cannot belong exclusively to one country or any particular individual (Sotshangane, 2002) and is fragmented across groups and national boundaries (McSweeney, 2000).

OBJECTIVE 3 CONCLUSION

After analysing the cultural dimensions of each participant based on different nationalities, only three out of eight participants believe that a person with high level of indulgence and individualism tend to be more involve in food photography. However, five out of eight participants do not particularly agree that food photography behaviour is closely linked with the nationality or cultural dimensions that they are in. In fact, according to Statista (2018a) (depicted in *Figure 2.2*), eight out of ten countries with the largest Instagram audiences worldwide are collectivist countries. Thus, based on the majority of participants and Hofstede criticism, *objective 3 established that it is not proven that a person with high level of indulgence and individualism culture tend to involve more in food photography compared to an individual of restraint and collectivism culture.*

4.3.4. OBJECTIVE 4: IMPORTANCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA FOR FOOD INDUSTRY

The practical recommendations for objective 4 will be further explain in section 5.2.

4.4. CONCLUSIONS

This chapter has analysed the research findings and fulfilled three objectives set by the researcher based on the total response of eight participants. Firstly, in terms of objective 1, there is a positive link between food photography on Instagram and food consumption behaviour between 18-29 years old. Next, objective 2 established that both intrinsic and extrinsic motivations mainly influence 18-29-year olds foodie's enthusiasm of posting food photography on Instagram. Finally, objective 3 found that it is not proven that a person with high level of indulgence and individualism culture tend to involve more in food photography compared to an individual of restraint and collectivism culture. The next chapter will present the overall conclusion of the research paper, including the practical recommendations of objective 4.

CHAPTER FIVE: FINAL CONCLUSIONS

5.1. SUMMARY

This study has investigated the global phenomenon of food photography particularly on Instagram, and how it correlates with the consumption behaviour of 18-29-year olds. This paper starts with the general introduction of food, food consumption, the rise of social media, food photography and finally sets out the aim and four main objectives for the research paper (the last objective is treated as practical recommendations discussed in Section 5.2 below). Furthermore, the literature review examines relevant theories behind the main objectives, such as; photography theory, consumption behaviour, motivation theories, and cultural dimension theories. Additionally, the result from the qualitative approach combination of semi-structured interview and photo-elicitation method have examined all the three objectives determined by the researcher. Based on the total participants of eight, objective 1 confirmed that there is a positive link between food photography on Instagram and food consumption behaviour of the target group. Moreover, the second objective established that both intrinsic and extrinsic motivations influences 18-29-year olds foodie's enthusiasm of posting food photography on Instagram. Finally, objective 3 found that it is not proven that a person with high level of indulgence and individualism culture tend to involve more in food photography compared to an individual of restraint and collectivism culture. Along with the finding and discussion, the new theories of self-determination theory (SDT), social engagement theory, and Hofstede criticism are also brought in to support the existing literature. The next section will provide several practical recommendations for the food industry, meeting the final objective of this paper.

5.2. PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATIONS

According to Andersson et al. (2015), there is a practical need for analysis to motivate customers in visiting a particular place for desired experience. Based on the fourth objective, this section will provide recommendations for food industry on how to engage more efficiently with the rise of social media and food consumption behaviour in the future. Firstly, when asked ‘*Have you ever set off to a restaurant right after you see food photos on your Instagram feed?*’ (See Appendix A), Deniz answered, ‘*Since most of the restaurants and cafes have their own Instagram, stalking them become like a new habit for me*’. This is coherent with the study by Hosie (2017), where it’s now normal to sit down in a restaurant having already decided what food to order since millennials have spent a few minutes stalking on Instagram in advance. Some participants such as Soha and Yazmin, are both aware that everyone is very tech-savvy nowadays and not having a social media account could become a huge weakness for restaurants (See Appendix L). Consistent with this, Jed Cartojano, the marketing director of multi-location California ice cream shop, *Afters Ice Cream*, is overwhelmed with the presence of Instagram and how it gives nothing but positive impact for the business: ‘*As a business, it’s a great platform to communicate your happenings and products*’ (An, 2018).

Therefore, the first recommendation for the food industry is to build ‘customer engagement’ through the adaptation of the marketing mix such as by taking advantage of new technologies and tools to serve customers. Haven (2007) indicated customer engagement as marketing’s ‘new key metric’ given the rapidly increasing online ‘media fragmentation’. Defined by Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick (2012), media fragmentation describes a trend towards increasing choice and consumption of different social media platforms. Thus, it is profoundly beneficial for companies to engage in more than one single touchpoint to better understand customers. Social media provides the opportunity to connect with customers using richer media with greater reach (Thackeray et al., 2008). Moreover, half of the participants (Soha, Su, Yazmin,

and Tadd), admitted that there will be some hesitations and reluctance involved to visit a café without an Instagram account where all participants believes that social media play a crucial role within the food industry. The interactive nature of these digital media not only allows restaurants to share and exchange information with customers but also allows customers to share and exchange with one another (Sashi, 2012). In fact, Tadd argued that the reason why having Instagram is important is because it allows him to ‘mention’ or share the restaurant’s contents to his friends that could eventually lead them to visit the restaurant.

The second recommendation is to constantly monitor and maintain an active Instagram presence, by creating compelling content and utilizing all Instagram features. This strategy is called ‘content marketing’ that focuses in the management of rich media and visualisation content that is aimed at engaging customers (Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick, 2012). Digital content marketing was defined by Pulizzi and Barrett (2008), where content created by the marketing team needs to be syndicated on various social platform to increase its visibility to a large audience (Vinerean, 2017). Specifically, the ability of utilizing all Instagram features such as Instagram stories and Instagram live will be beneficial to showcase new foods or signature beverages. In terms of the content, when inquired, ‘*do you follow any food bloggers? any cafes/restaurants?*’, Mhen answered ‘*I followed Starbucks because their feed is very good! very colourful and eye catching, which makes it so fun to follow!*’. This shows that Starbucks is responding to the customers’ expectation through their aesthetically pleasing contents (Garcia, 2017). Another example of a successful social media presence is by *Pietro Nolita*, a ‘healthy Italian’ Manhattan restaurant. *Pietro Nolita* successfully utilised Instagram to help lure customers from around the world with its ‘all pink designs’ feature and catchy phrases, that has a tremendous Instagram following of nearly 19,000 just in a year (*Picture 5.1* below).

Picture 5.1. Pietro Nolita's unique Instagram feed ²

The third recommendation is to encourage customers to be a part of the digital promotion through hashtag strategy and social media sharing. Using hashtags will undoubtedly increase a restaurant's popularity, exposure and most importantly, restaurants are able to fit hashtags based on their own specific appeal or image that they want to portray, such as: *#healthyfood* or *#localfood*. Carah and Shaul (2015) found that engagement not only takes the form of likes and comments, but also pauses on particular images and tapping on hashtags. Users can generate a flow of images in the explore feed by searching for a hashtag that helps restaurants to be more visible and accessible to consumers. In terms of social media sharing, marketing managers can

² Permission to use this Instagram content was granted by the company, they requested 'You can go ahead and screenshot my page, but, to be clear, this restaurant was inspired by pastel colors of the italian riviera and from the menphis group, a movement that was born in 1980's in milan where the owner is from.'

encourage customers to post photos in several ways such as by sponsoring an Instagram contest with award prizes or offering exclusive coupons to the best photos. Encouraging Instagram posts is highly recommended as it will keep customers loyal, actively engaged and automatically promoting the restaurant. This combination of rational and emotional factors of visual elements has been designed for persuasion, accessibility and performance, which often referred as ‘online customer experience’ strategy (Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick, 2012). Suggested by de Chernatony (2001), *Figure 5.1* below shows factors that influence the online customer experience in a pyramid form of success factors.

Figure 5.1. The online customer experience pyramid – success factors

(Source: de Chernatony, 2001)

5.3. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE STUDY

The study acknowledges the existence of limitations throughout the research. Firstly, the researcher intended to cover all factors behind the relationship between food photography and food consumption behaviour, all the motivations behind the foodie culture and social media as well as the linkage between food photography behaviour and all the six Hofstede's cultural dimensions. However, due to limited time and access, the researcher's intentions became overloaded and could not be explored deeply, leading to the simplification of all the objectives. In terms of the literature, as food photography and social media are still an emerging target of study, there is a limited amount of theories on the topic related to the food culture and food visuals on social media, which affects the ability to support the present study. Moreover, Hofstede's cultural dimensions presented in the current study is also argued to be outdated in supporting the global phenomenon of food photography. In fact, most of the participants are international students that have been culturally influenced around the world, leading to the dilution of their original cultural values. In the future, the 2004 research project of GLOBE study that was designed to expand Hofstede's 1980 work of 5 to 18 dimensions (Hofstede, 2006), should be adopted to better analyse the behaviour of today's rapidly changing global environments and modern value. Additionally, cultural understanding and familiarity of cultural specific behaviours would help researchers to conduct the study more easily in a time-efficient manner. It is also recommended to apply the ethical guidelines from a cross-cultural perspective and cultural differences.

In terms of the methodology, the researcher was constantly challenged with the practical issues of photo-elicitation interviews, especially throughout the whole transcribing process, since both textual and visual aspects have to be analysed. Although most participants talked enthusiastically about their food photographs and were very expressive during the photo experience, this was not always the case. For instance, when asked to explain more about a

picture (See *Picture 5.2*), the participant inattentively answered, ‘*It was on my friend’s birthday, it’s just..looks nice, I guess*’. This expression was certainly difficult to put into words since the participant gave the impression that this particular photo could speak by itself. In the future, researchers need to be ready to deal with different types of methodological and practical challenges through consistent practices. One way is to conduct a pilot study prior the practice to identify weaknesses throughout the process and assess the feasibility of the right research strategy. At the end of the study, researchers can also have informal discussions with each participant which could identify areas of improvement or amendment. Moreover, due to the subjective and ambiguous nature of qualitative research (Atieno, 2009), future study would have to consider other approaches to offer more definite outcomes such as questionnaires with closed-ended questions or experiment with a control group.

Picture 5.2. Su: ‘it’s just..looks nice, I guess’

In terms of sample size, there are only eight participants, which were not likely to be representative for the whole target group of 18-29-year olds. Given that participants are those with high interest of food (i.e. foodie), many people who do not identify themselves as a member of this specific group were not counted as eligible to participate in this study. This factor limited the sample size and made it more challenging to find suitable participants. Since the sample size of this study is limited, a larger sample through ‘snowball sampling’ are necessary to better justify the global phenomenon of food photography. Snowball sampling is eminently suggested as this is the simplest sampling method that involves primary respondents nominating other potential respondents to the researchers (Atkinson and Flint, 2001) and commonly apply to locate hidden populations (Johnson, 2014).

5.4. SUMMARY OF CONCLUSIONS

Despite the limitations, this paper provides useful insights of food photography and consumption behaviour, especially through two main motivation theories and cultural dimensions, which are the areas that have not yet been well-studied. Furthermore, this paper presents several practical recommendations that are efficiently attainable for food industry. Beyond the successful completion of four main objectives, this paper aims to motivate future researchers to look beyond this topic and generate new theories behind the global phenomenon of food photography that are believed to be an emerging topic in today’s popular culture.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

An initial list of questions has been discussed and feedback have been given by the supervisor.

Introductory (broad) questions:

- What do you think about social media nowadays?
- What is your favourite social media platform?
- Tell me about the social media you use and how you use it?
- Are you familiar with Instagram and how it works? – how do you use Instagram (as if, what is your Instagram for?)
- How often do you use Instagram?
- What do you post on Instagram? What do you usually like or comment on Instagram?
- Do you observe what your friends, or others are doing on Instagram?
- What kind of people that you follow on Instagram? Do they affect your behaviour?

Food photography (FP):

- When was this? Do you remember this occasion?
- How often do you take pictures before you eat?
- What is your favourite food to photograph?
- What are the types of food photos you shared online?
- What triggers you in taking pictures before you eat? do you feel satisfied?
- How many photos (roughly) do you take for one dish before you decide that you have the right shots?

FP on Instagram:

- Do you always put your food photo on Instagram (either story/post)?

- So, what happened next? What do you expect to get from putting your food photos in Instagram?
- How often did you do photograph your food without posting it on Instagram?
- Within a week, how often did you spend browsing food images on Instagram?
- Have you ever triggered to eat when you see those food photos? (from friends' post or any food-related account you followed)

Consumption:

- Pausing to take picture before you eat could make your food get cold, does it really matter to you?
- 'US researchers found that the effects of photographing food can make it less enjoyable to eat' (Gander, 2017)– do you agree with this statement? (explain why)
- Does taking picture somehow triggers you to eat more or you never really realize anything?

Peer/culture questions:

- Have you ever (at least once) think about the opinion of your friends around you when you Instagram your food?
- Would you be reluctant to take pictures in front of others or it doesn't really matter? (or vice versa - what do you think about people who Instagram food when you are having a meal?)
- Do you ever think that your behaviour (which is taking picture before you eat) relates to the country that you are coming from?

Restaurants:

- In terms of your actual dining experience, have you ever set off to a restaurant right after you see food photos on your Instagram feed?

- What do you do before you decided to come to a restaurant? (do you check the menu online? Checking up their Instagram feed)
- Do you think that it's important for restaurants to have their own social media account, especially Instagram?
- Will you be more attracted to visit a café/restaurant that has their own Instagram account or it doesn't really matter? (if yes, will you be reluctant then to come to a restaurant without Instagram account)

APPENDIX B: CONSENT FORM

Consent Form – Confidential Data

This form is for you to state whether or not you agree to take part in this interview. Please take some time to read and answer every question carefully. If there is anything you do not understand, or if you want more information, please **do not hesitate** to ask me.

	YES	NO
Have I explained why I want to talk to you?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Do you agree that all the information provided will be held confidentially?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Do you agree that your identity will not be revealed and will stay anonymous?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Have you had an opportunity to ask questions about today's talk?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Do you understand that the information you provide will be held in confidence by the interviewer?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Do you understand that you may withdraw from the chat at any time and for any reason?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Do you agree to take part in the interview?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
If yes, do you agree to your interviews being recorded? (You may take part in the study without agreeing to this).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Do you agree that participation in this study is entirely voluntary and that you can withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Interviewee name (in BLOCK letters):

Interviewee signature:

Interviewer's name:

Date: _____

**ONE COPY FOR INTERVIEWEE & ONE COPY TO BE RETAINED BY
INTERVIEWER**

APPENDIX C: TYPE AND PURPOSE OF QUESTIONS

Type of Questions	Purpose of Questions
Introductory questions	Yield spontaneous and rich descriptions of the phenomena investigated (Kvale and Brinkmann, 2009).
Follow-up questions	Prepared to elaborate and ensure optimal responses together with reassuring noises and interjections (Leech, 2002).
Structuring questions	To keeping the interview structured and to refer the use of key questions
Specifying questions	To develop more precise descriptions from general statements (Qu and Dumay, 2013).
Interpreting questions	To rephrase and clarify the interviewees' answer rather than exploring new information.

APPENDIX D: CODE INITIALISATION AND THEME IDENTIFIED

Due to anonymity principle, the interviewer is denoted as 'I' and the participants as 'P'. Some words have also been formalised from the original transcript in order to avoid confusion.

CODE INITIALISATION 1

91 I: pausing to take picture before you eat cold make your food gets cold, does
92 it really matter to you?

93 P8: (chuckles) it depends on how hungry i am! if it looks really really good
94 i will still take a picture of it but im more likely to rush because i just want
95 to eat it! but then sometimes, like if you are in a group setting and all your
96 friends want to take photos, is kind of down to how long all of us take photo
97 rather than just myself, so you have to be considerate of others as well.

98 I: alright! fair enough! in relation to that i'm interested in finding your
99 response to this statement, 'US researchers found that the effects of
100 photographing food can make it less enjoyable to eat' (Gander, 2017). do
101 you agree or disagree to this question?

102 P8: mmm, i disagree. because i feel like its two different unrelated actions.
103 i think the only time we make it not enjoyable to eat is if you order
104 something for the sake of taking photo of it but i never order something
105 unless genuinely want to eat it. so taking a photo always makes me want
106 to eat it. - and i'm not going to spend like 5 minutes taking a photo probably
107 going to spend 2 minutes maximum and then eat straight away so...yeah. it
108 doesn't seem to lose much value for me.

109 I: okay fair enough! that's a really good answer! some people told me that
110 when they take picture, they will try to take the best angle, which makes
111 them really want to eat it more. do you agree with it? which is the other way
112 around from the statement we discuss earlier.

113 P8: mmm...I feel sometimes it takes effort to get a really nice picture well...
114 most of the time, even when take the picture of the food, i'm not really a
115 100% happy with how it looks in the photo but like... i don't really care
116 enough to take the best photo possible. i just want to take the photo that
117 resembles and captures the best light and i'm not going to be bothered if it
118 does not look perfect or it does not look like the way i wanted to. because
119 yeah i rather just start eating..

Line Extract, with code initialisation	
Line Number	Coded for
93 – 94	Taking picture depends on certain situation
95	Taking picture within a group setting situation
96 – 97	Behavioural consideration within a group setting
102	Opinion that food photography and consumption behaviour are two different things
103 – 106	The reason why participant disagree with the statement asked
107 – 108	Usual time spend in taking photo and value of the food
113 – 115	Effort of nice picture and how the participant deal with it
116 – 117	Intrinsic motivation of food photography
118 – 119	Unwillingness of getting the best picture

Themes Identified:

Consumption Behaviour
Motivation of food photography

CODE INITIALISATION 2

120 I: that is interesting to know. Is food photography a huge thing in China?

121 P3: yes. Although I never done a research about that but judging from my
 122 friends and my family, we all take pictures and post it on social media
 123 especially Instagram. Also, to add on that, I think because of globalization
 124 and how easy it is nowadays to access internet and information from it. All
 125 the exposure makes it easy to support why food photograph is very popular!
 126 Chinese people also, in my opinion, do not only want to share their life, but
 127 there is also another factor. They want other people to see that they are in a
 128 good stage of life, it is the better than you thinking, I feel like. So yeah.
 129 although I do not always think that way, I believe that the culture
 130 unconsciously has an impact on me.

131 I: great! It is always interesting to learn more about other cultures other than
 132 your own! So, in what other occasion that you find yourself involved in food
 133 photography?

134 P3: well, every time I go out to be honest! Hmm, actually, my friends
 135 and I keep going to the same restaurants and I still take photo. They asked
 136 why I always pictures since we always order the same thing. And I always
 137 say that that's what makes it special because this is taken in a different
 138 moment. Since then, my friends understand that treasure every moment
 139 and they always let me to take photos!

140 I: oh, that's really nice! What a good way in putting it! do you think that
 141 your habit of taking picture before you eat relates to the country that you are
 142 coming from?

143 P3: before I answer it I just want to say that most of the questions that you
 144 asked are actually the questions that I never think before. (chuckles) but to
 145 answer your question, yes, I think it definitely is. Because I grow up with
 146 the community that always care about what other people are doing,
 147 especially friends and family. So, I really want to share what I eat in
 148 Instagram to show my friends and family about my updates. We are very
 149 family-oriented and yeah Chinese culture definitely have an impact on me.

150 I: sweet! It's always interesting to learn more about other cultures other than
 151 your own!

Line Extract, with code initialisation	
Line Number	Coded for
121-122	Realising that everyone in the surroundings take pictures
123-124	Globalization and access of internet triggers food photography
125	Popularity of food photography for Chinese people
126-129	Several factors of food photography in China and how it has an impact on the participant
133-134	Habit of going to the same restaurants and food photography with friends
135-137	Intrinsic reasons of food photography
142-143	The community behaviour and impact
144	Friends and family as an important aspect of food photography
145-146	Impact on Chinese culture on the participant

Themes Identified:

Cultural Impact or dimension

Motivation of food photography

CODE INITIALISATION 3

161 I: will you be reluctant to come to a restaurant without an Instagram
162 account?

163 P4: yes, I will be reluctant since I am the type of person that keep following
164 and want to see what people commented on Instagram to check the service,
165 the food, the pictures – it’s very important then, to see what other people
166 experience!

167 So, are you saying that having an Instagram account is important for
168 restaurants?

169 P4: yes very, very important! everyone has a smartphone and most of the
170 places have an Instagram account people are looking for quality and it’s
171 important for a restaurant to offer what they got to make customers
172 confidence to visit the place, and also because I would like to see at least an
173 idea about what I’m going to order. If I can’t find any social media
174 associated with them, this will impact me a lot because how about if it’s my
175 first time visiting this café? How would I know that this place is good
176 enough? I don’t want to spend my time or money!

177 I: that is true, I agree with you. If you don’t any information online, how
178 could you compete with your competitors! And as you said before, everyone
179 has a smartphone and companies should use this opportunity!

180 P4: yeah, and also because in this kind of business, they have to be
181 modernized, otherwise just prepare to die because no one is going to know
182 about the place. people are very active with looking food photos online, in
183 order to find out more about food! We all prefer to look beforehand, so
184 yeah... if you want to have enough customers I think it’s important.

185 I: yes, I completely agree. Okay this brings me to the final question; do you
186 think that food photography is a global phenomenon?

187 P4: yes completely. Now everyone has a smartphone it is part of the
188 technology. Everyone’s driven by what people and what social media says
189 about the prices or places. everyone wants to keep updated so yes, I believe
190 that if restaurants or any food business consider this kind of trends they will
191 have more responses to customers and they will have better income since
192 they will attract people that love food!

Line Extract, with code initialisation	
Line Number	Coded for
163-166	Reluctance factors to visit restaurants without an Instagram account
169 -170	Awareness of online trend in food industry
171 – 173	Importance of restaurants to have an Instagram account
174 – 176	Personal reasons given to food industry without social media
180 – 181	How modernization impact food industry
182 – 183	The behaviour of people in the online platform
184	Benefit of having social media
187 – 189	The popularity of smartphone and technology advancement
190 – 192	Opportunity of utilizing social media account and understanding the online trend

Themes Identified:

Social media importance

Food industry on social media

APPENDIX E: VIRTUAL REPRESENTATION OF RELEVANT THEMES

Model 1: Thematic Map of Consumption Behaviour

Model 2: Thematic Map of Food Photography Motivation

Model 3: Thematic Map of Cultural Impact or Dimension

Model 4: Thematic Map of Social Media Importance

Model 5: Thematic Map of Food Industry on Social Media

APPENDIX F: RESPONSES TO GANDER (2017) STATEMENT

Responses to the statement: 'US researchers found that the effects of photographing food can make it less enjoyable to eat' (Gander, 2017)				
No.	Participants	Agree	Disagree	Response
1.	Deniz		✓	<i>'Because definitely I take a picture of food if it looks eatable, tasty. This is why I take the picture. So, it's actually the other way around, I may be biased but it actually makes the food tastier.'</i>
2.	Soha	Somewhat in Between		<i>'It depends. I would say it would go both ways depending what I'm eating and what I'm photographing!'</i>
3.	Su		✓	<i>'You want to remember what you eat, well at least for me. for me, it's pointless if you do not take photo! We all have smartphones it wouldn't take that long. It's not like we are waiting to set up the camera or anything.'</i>
4.	Yazmin		✓	<i>'I actually think that taking picture makes it more enjoyable to eat because every cuisine is different, I love eating out especially for different kinds of food from different countries and taking a picture as a memory is important to me. so, yeah, I believe that taking picture will have no bad impact on a taste or less enjoyable.'</i>

5.	Natalie		✓	<i>'I don't think taking photos before I eat would influence my enjoyment to eat... so I think would disagree!'</i>
6.	Tadd	✓		<i>'I don't really take photo that much but thinking back or when I go to a restaurant with friends, when I need to wait for them to take photo when I was hungry, I don't think I would enjoy the food as much... so yeah I think I agree.'</i>
7.	Mhen		✓	<i>'For me, I disagree, because I think, when you got a good photo, you will be very happy.... I believe that if you are happy, you will perceive the food really good as well – I will not take a photo when the food is ugly! that's why I said presentation is really good because it could attract you to enjoy your food more...'</i>
8.	Mitty		✓	<i>'I disagree. because I feel like its two different, unrelated actions. I think the only time we make it not enjoyable to eat is if you order something for the sake of taking photo.'</i>

APPENDIX G: KEY RESPONSES OF OBJECTIVE 1

No.	Participants	Findings	Key Responses
1.	Deniz	Positive Link	<i>'Good food photography convinced me that the food is good!'</i>
2.	Soha	Positive Link	<i>'I always have that craving and looking at my friends' post triggers me a lot!'</i>
3.	Su	Positive Link	<i>'When I add filters on, it makes the food looks so much better, which actually increase my appetite!'</i>
4.	Yazmin	Positive Link	<i>'I always take the best angle and it somehow makes me more attracted to the food, it opens my appetite.'</i>
5.	Natalie	No Link	<i>'Your eyesight is better than any other things like your smartphone.'</i>
6.	Tadd	No Link	<i>'I go to restaurants with pretty food but it doesn't taste as good. So, I mean like, it has nothing to do with my consumption.'</i>
7.	Mhen	Positive Link	<i>'When you got a good photo, you will be very happy. I believe that if you are happy, you will perceive the food really good as well!'</i>
8.	Mitty	No Link	<i>'I just want to take photo that resembles and captures the best light... I'm not going to be bothered if it does not look perfect or look like the way I wanted to as I will eat them anyway...'</i>

APPENDIX H: KEY RESPONSES OF OBJECTIVE 2 (INTRINSIC)

No.	Participants	Key Responses
1.	Deniz	<i>'I don't really care about how many people that like or comments on my food photos because it's all about me enjoying the moment. If I compare with my selfies or just me in the picture, there will always more likes on it. I always know that food picture and if I wasn't there, I will always get less likes. But I don't mind that and it really doesn't matter!'</i>
2.	Natalie	<i>'Well, I wouldn't post it for people actually. I don't really expect people to like or commented on my Instagram, simply like, just telling them what I like.'</i>
3.	Mitty	<i>'I think my Instagram posts are more like my 'virtual diary' rather than for other people to see it... so it was more for the sake of just keeping it on my own accountability, rather than for other people to see it.'</i>
4.	Soha*	<i>'Food photography is like a 'souvenir' for me. So obviously when I'm with my friends, I took food pictures as a souvenir that I went out with them. I don't care about what they think so I'm just doing it for myself here!'</i>
5.	Su*	<i>'What makes it special is that my food posts are always taken in many different moments and I treasure every moment of myself.'</i>
6.	Yazmin*	<i>'I always photograph my food but I don't always post them as I took them to remember the moment, as my memories.'</i>
7.	Tadd*	<i>'I don't really care about their likes/comments... just kind of...like post them for satisfying myself.'</i>

**Participants were influenced by both intrinsic and extrinsic motivations*

APPENDIX I: KEY RESPONSES OF OBJECTIVE 2 (EXTRINSIC)

No.	Participants	Key Responses
1.	Mhen	<i>'In places like Bettys, for example, I post it on Instagram not just to show them that I dine it there but expecting their likes because it shows me that my photo is good enough.'</i>
2.	Soha*	<i>'I can't always send my pictures to all my friends, I would just say that Instagram is a place to show everyone what is up. I'm doing it as a showcase, for everyone to see it!'</i>
3.	Su*	<i>'I hope I get as much likes as possible. I want people to agree to my choice but if it's not, I would try to accept it since everyone has a different opinion.'</i>
4.	Yazmin*	<i>'I post because I care and want to find out about what people feel about my food photos. I'm interested in what they think, which is through the comments they wrote for me!'</i>
5.	Tadd*	<i>'I love to share with my friends. I love to tell them what is going on, what I'm doing in my life. Because you rarely meet them since everyone travels all over the place.'</i>
<i>*Participants were influenced by both intrinsic and extrinsic motivations</i>		

APPENDIX J: PARTICIPANTS WITH INDIVIDUALISM AND INDULGENCE
CULTURES

No.	Participants	Objective 3	Nationality	Findings
1.	Natalie	Proved	USA	<i>'In the US, everyone is very active with Instagram, especially during events like Coachella and I would say in develop country like the US, food photography will be more involved than developing or less developing countries.'</i>
2.	Tadd	Proved	Australia	<i>'At least for us, the Australians, we all take heaps of pictures and that is what we all do, every time I visit a café, at least one person is taking photo or posting their food photo or videos on Instagram stories, even the smallest thing like avocado on toast... it's such an undeniable behaviour.'</i>
3.	Mitty	Not proven	United Kingdom	<i>'I never think that it's a country thing. It's just more of the cultural generation rather than just a country. today's generation has their own smartphones and there's no reluctance to take photos since everyone is doing it especially in our generation.'</i>

APPENDIX K: PARTICIPANTS WITH COLLECTIVISM AND RESTRAINT
CULTURES

No.	Participants	Objective 3	Nationality	Findings
1.	Deniz	Proved	Turkey	<i>'My friends told me that 'you are always eating!' and this makes me feel so bad and guilty about it so I just started to share which one is my favourite one!'</i>
2.	Soha	Not proven	India	<i>'I'm always with a group of comfortable people, so I always think that they wouldn't mind of me taking a picture as we are all like-minded people that perceive food photography as tray of togetherness.'</i>
3.	Su	Not proven	China	<i>'I only eat with my closest friends and they know me well, everyone is doing it, we all have the same habit of taking pictures so they never judge me or anything.'</i>
4.	Mhen	Not proven	Thailand	<i>'Nowadays, it's very easy to see what other countries are doing... we are bored and we always look out for others, in case that's what happened to me, thanks to the internet. I think this phenomenon is even bigger compared to here or other countries.'</i>

APPENDIX L: KEY RESPONSES TO THE QUESTION

Responses to the question: <i>do you think that it's important for restaurants to have their own social media account, especially Instagram?</i>			
No.	Participants	Objective 4	Key Responses
1.	Deniz	Important	<i>'Absolutely. It's actually important for them to increase their public relations. It is required in a way because I always believe that good cafe is the one with a good publicity in the end!'</i>
2.	Soha	Important	<i>'I definitely think that they should have one! Especially nowadays with everyone being so tech-savvy and everyone wants to see when and where it's happening. Good Instagram feed will attract more customers since Instagram allows the consumer to share food photos among their friends.'</i>
3.	Su	Important	<i>'Yes. I'm studying marketing and if restaurants don't put much effort on social media they will never be known let alone, popular.'</i>
4.	Yazmin	Important	<i>'It's very important! everyone has a smartphone and most of the places have an Instagram account. People are looking for quality and it's important for a restaurant to offer what they got to increase customers confidence before visit the place.'</i>

5.	Natalie	Important	<i>‘I think obviously yes because Instagram or any other social media is a potential way that they can use to reach their customers, because obviously the more ways you get yourself out there, means the more people know about you and the more likely you get people to visit.’</i>
6.	Tadd	Important	<i>‘Absolutely! It’s very important to have social media especially Instagram account these days. It’s a good way to keep the customers up to date and looking at the pictures of food can entice people to go there more often!’</i>
7.	Mhen	Important	<i>‘Well, my family business is something related with food industry so I think when we take photos, it’s a really good way to appeal customer to go there and try those beautiful food.’</i>
8.	Mitty	Important	<i>‘For me, yes. Especially if there is a specific dish that I really want to eat. I always look through Instagram just to find the best restaurant that sell that specific dish and looking at those photos makes me really hungry, and triggers me to eat whenever that photo is showing.’</i>